

DEFINITE-CCRI

Report on methodology for the TIP and technical due diligence

(Deliverable 4.1)

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Author(s)	Eleni Kanellou (NTUA), Evi Makri (NTUA)
Reviewer(s)	All partners
Contributor(s)	Nikolai Jacobi (ICLEI), Malen Otero (ICLEI), Marijana Novak (CE)
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DEFINITE-CCRI

DEFINITE-CCRI - Deal Engine, with finance, investment and technical expertise for the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative

Executive Summary

The report on methodology for the TIP and technical due diligence is the first deliverable of Work Package 4, within the umbrella of the DEFINITE-CCRI project. This document reports on the technological and impact assessment related components of the CCRI Deal Brokerage methodology, covering the methodology, assessment criteria, guidance document, excel sheets, etc.

The document includes:

- **Circular economy monitoring frameworks and indicators:** A short description of the prevailing circular economy monitoring frameworks and indicators in the academic literature and in policy fronts is given.
- **The Definite-CCRI technical and impact potential assessment:** The easy to customise framework that is developed within the Definite-CCRI project is presented. The aim of the framework is to easily assess the technical and innovation potential as well as the impact with regards to the circularity, the environment, the society, and the macro-economic level. The process and the timeline of the TIP for the circular economy projects is detailed.
- **Technical Due Diligence Support:** In this section the services provided in the due diligence phase are detailed. Specifically, the details of the feasibility study, the technology roadmapping exercise, and the stakeholder mapping and engagement process are presented. Details on the 2-day intensive bilateral consultation sessions with the projects are given.

DEFINITE Consortium Partners

Logo	Organisation	Type	Country
	ICLEI EURO	Small and medium-sized enterprise	Germany
	Circle Economy	Non-governmental organisation	The Netherlands
	Stad Gent	Municipality	Belgium
	Bankers without Boundaries (BwB)	Non-governmental organisation	Ireland
	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA)	University	Greece

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The DEFINITE-CCRI Project in a Nutshell

Effective investment and financing opportunities for circular economy projects in Europe are still few. For securing financing, circular economy projects must meet investors' requirements for bankability and display risk-return profiles to increase investors' trust in impactful projects aimed at advancing the transition to a more circular economy in cities and regions. In order to become less risky and more appealing for investments, projects need to be developed around new and re-designed finance solutions and business models. Transaction costs need to be decreased and the private finance community needs to be engaged to address legal, administrative and market related challenges. In response to this, the DEFINITE-CCRI project establishes a Deal Engine Mechanism, providing technical, financial, and circular economy expertise through local Project Development Assistance (PDA) in an unprecedented and streamlined process to city and regional governments and to project developers. It aims to co-create and prove an end-to-end PDA process, aggregating risk mitigation, EU Taxonomy compliance, circularity criteria and technical and financial engineering in a single project development service for the CCRI's service portfolio. This will inject the financial, technical, and managerial know-how into urban circular transitions and ultimately contribute to lower virgin non-renewable material use, lower GHG emissions and more just and inclusive circular employment in line with the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and the Bio-economy Strategy.

DEFINITE-CCRI (*Deal Engine, with finance, investment and technical expertise for the European Commission's Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – CCRI*) is a Horizon Europe funded project that has started in November 2022.

DEFINITE-CCRI Objectives

The four key objectives at the foundation of the project's vision and work plan are:

- **Objective 1:** To build and operate a deal engine for the CCRI and establish it as a sustainable service offering for cities in Europe.
- **Objective 2:** To close the gap between circular economy projects in cities and regions and investors and finance partners, and to mitigate investment risks for circular economy projects.
- **Objective 3:** To increase the investment viability of innovative, high-impact circularity projects by mitigating risk and increasing their investment readiness.
- **Objective 4:** To successfully launch four investments in circular economy projects up to 20 million Euro investment volume per project in CCRI cities and regions.

Introduction

The concept of the circular economy is an emerging paradigm seeking to establish a sustainable model that decouples economic growth from resource consumption [1]. By implementing circular economy models, new business opportunities are expected, accompanied by a significant enhancement in resource efficiency within current systems. The prevailing linear ("take-make-dispose") production model is connected with substantial waste, whereas circular economy models advocate restorative and regenerative approaches to minimise waste along the value chain [1].

The 2030's Agenda adopted by the world leaders in 2015, represents the new global sustainable development framework and sets 17 sustainable development goals (SDGs) [2], one of which is goal 11: "Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable" and goal 12: "Responsible Consumption and Production". Within the specific targets of goal 11 is to improve urban planning and enhance resilience to environmental impacts in cities and human settlements while goal 12 focuses on encouraging companies, especially large and transnational ones, to adopt sustainable practices and integrate sustainability information into their reporting cycle.

The European Commission (EC) is fully committed to achieving the SDGs and has devised dedicated strategies and directives to this end [3]. In 2015, the EC adopted an ambitious Circular Economy Action Plan, encompassing measures to propel Europe's transition towards a circular economy, boosting global competitiveness, fostering sustainable economic growth, and generating new employment opportunities [4]. In 2019, the EC renewed this plan, adding future challenges in shaping the economy and paving the way towards a climate-neutral, circular economy with minimized pressure on natural resources, freshwater, and ecosystems.

The Circular Economy Action Plan, aimed at contributing to the "Responsible Consumption and Production" goal, lies at the heart of the EC's approach [4] and is one of the cornerstones of the EU Green Deal, Europe's plan to transform the continent to a resource efficient and sustainable economy [5]. The plan aligns closely with key EU policy priorities and global efforts towards sustainable development. It seeks to facilitate the transition from a linear to a circular economic model in Europe and is accompanied by directives providing clear instructions to member states and industries alike.

In the Circular Economy Action Plan, circular economy is defined as: "an economy where the value of products, materials and resources is maintained in the economy for as long as possible, and the generation of waste is minimised" [6]. Circular economy models, inspired by nature's ecosystem, ensure that no materials are wasted, and products are designed for remanufacturing, reuse, or refurbishment after consumption [6]. This approach extends the lifespan of components and retains their value as potential input for another process, contrasting with the traditional linear "take, make, dispose" model of production.

At the same time, cities and regions are the governance level that is closest to citizens [7]. They have the potential to innovate and contribute to a socio-economic transition establishing circular ecosystems

within their region. Cities and regions can be drivers of change contributing to a sustainable, regenerative, and inclusive circular economy. Many of them have already plans in motion aiming at enhancing their circularity while improving their local systems and economies. While policy tools and some funding instruments are in place, there are some gaps in knowledge, information, and skills as well as in attracting investors to circular economy projects.

The DEFINITE-CCRI project aims to bridge that gap enabling circular projects in a city level to become more bankable. The project aims to demonstrate the bankability of high-impact circularity projects and increase maturity and investor trust in circular economy innovation. To do so it will provide an end-to-end project development assistance (PDA) process, aggregating risk-mitigation, EU Taxonomy compliance, circularity criteria and technical and financial engineering in a single project development service for the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative's (CCRI) service portfolio. As a result, financial, technical, and managerial expertise will be injected into urban circular transitions and contribute to lower virgin non-renewable material use, lower GHG emissions and more just and inclusive circular employment in line with the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and the Bioeconomy Strategy.

This deliverable aims at focusing on the technical and Impact potential assessment for the DEFINITE-CCRI project. Specifically, the related methodology and assessment criteria are developed based on available methodologies resulting to a flexible toolbox. The DEFINITE-CCRI technical assessment toolbox will be part of the Deal Brokerage and will be used to enable projects to advance the EU Green Deal in line with the EU Taxonomy, the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, and the European bioeconomy strategy. Furthermore, the technical due diligence support package and the process of project appraisal is detailed defining what, when and how the respective technical and impact project development assistance (PDA) and support will be carried out.

This report is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 outlines the theoretical background, presenting some of policies at EU level that aim at accelerating circular economy as well as some of the existing circular economy monitoring frameworks and indicator sets in a brief overview of the existing literature, related methodologies, and assessment criteria.
- Chapter 3 presents the DEFINITE CCRI simple framework that is to be employed for the technical impact potential assessment of the project development assistance phase.
- Chapter 4 presents the technical due diligence support package and the stepwise process that will be followed during the project appraisal, defining how the respective PDA support will be carried out.
- Chapter 5 concludes the deliverable at hand.

Circular economy monitoring frameworks and indicators

Framing circular economy, definitions, and policies

Circular economy is an emerging paradigm and some attempts to define the concept have been made both in a policy level, in an industry level, and in academia. The European Commission within the EU Action Plan for Circular Economy defines circular economy as "a systemic approach to economic development designed to benefit businesses, society, and the environment [8]. It aims to gradually decouple economic activity from the consumption of finite resources and design waste out of the system. It promotes greater resource productivity, sustainable growth, and generates new business opportunities. The Ellen MacArthur Foundation defines circular economy as "an industrial system that is restorative or regenerative by intention and design. It replaces the end-of-life concept with restoration, shifts towards the use of renewable energy, eliminates the use of toxic chemicals, and aims for the elimination of waste through the superior design of materials, products, systems, and business models [9]."

Stahel defines circular economy as "an economy that is not based on the extraction of raw materials but on the delivery of functions or performance" [10]. Geissdoerfer et al. define it as "an economic system that is restorative and regenerative by intention and design replacing the traditional linear 'take-make-dispose' model with new processes that are restorative and regenerative, aiming to keep products, components, and materials at their highest utility and value at all times [11]. Fraccascia et al. defines it as "an industrial system that is powered by renewable energy, where materials and products are designed to be reused, repaired, remanufactured, or recycled to create a closed-loop system" [12]. Ghisellini et al. define circular economy as "a production and consumption model that involves sharing, leasing, reusing, repairing, refurbishing, and recycling existing materials and products for as long as possible to create a closed-loop system, minimizing the use of resource inputs and the creation of waste, pollution, and carbon emissions" [13].

From a policy perspective, circular economy is one the main building blocks of the European Green Deal, Europe's agenda for sustainable growth [14]. The EU Green Deal aims at making Europe the first climate neutral continent in the world. It aims to boost the efficient use of resources by moving to clean energy, and circular economy practices while mitigating climate change, reverting biodiversity loss, and cutting pollution [15]. It is setting the EU on a path to reach its climate targets by 2030 in a fair, cost effective and competitive way. All 27 EU Member States are committed to turning the EU into the first climate neutral continent by 2050. The transition aims to create new opportunities for innovation, investment, and jobs, as well as reduce emissions, address energy poverty, reduce external energy dependence and improve citizens' health and wellbeing.

To further enhance the transition to circular economy the European Commission has established the **Circular Economy Action Plan** (CEAP) [16]. It is a comprehensive body of legislative and non-legislative actions adopted in 2015, aiming at transitioning the European economy from a linear to a circular model. The Action Plan mapped out 54 actions, as well as four legislative proposals on waste. It includes an

inclusive set of initiatives aiming at promoting circular economy and it includes measures to make products more sustainable, reduce waste, and overall promote circular business models. The European Commission adopted the new CEAP in March 2020, which is one of the main building blocks of the European Green Deal. The plan aims to reduce the EU's consumption footprint and double its circular material use rate in the coming decade. More specifically, the focus will lie on high-impact value, namely on electronics and ICT, batteries and vehicles, packaging, plastics, construction and buildings, food, water, and nutrients.

To further contribute to achieving the goals of the EU Green Deal a **European bioeconomy strategy** was established [17]. The bioeconomy strategy aims to accelerate the deployment of a sustainable European bioeconomy. It contributes to the European Green Deal, as well as industrial, circular economy and clean energy innovation strategies. The bioeconomy covers all sectors and systems that rely on biological resources (animals, plants, micro-organisms, and derived biomass, including organic waste), their functions and principles. It includes and links land and marine ecosystems and the services they provide.

To translate the climate and environmental objectives into criteria for specific economic activities for sustainable investment purposes the European Commission has established the **EU Taxonomy** [18], an EU-wide classification system for sustainable investments. 'Transition to Circular Economy' is one of the 6 environmental objectives that underline the EU Taxonomy pillars, along with Climate Change mitigation, Climate Change Adaptation, Sustainable Use and Protection of Water and Marine Resources, Pollution and Prevention Control and Protection and Restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems. Key sectors of the EU Taxonomy pillar on Circular Economy include Agriculture and Forestry, Manufacturing, Electricity and Gas supply, Water and Sewage, Transport, IT, and Buildings.

There are some key EU policies in place aiming at accelerating the circular economy transition apart from the Circular Economy Action Plan. The Waste Framework directive includes a legal framework for waste management in the EU along with waste prevention measures, recycling targets and waste hierarchy principles [19]. The Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive aims at reducing the environmental impact of packaging waste through specific recovery and recycling targets, eco-design requirements, and using recycled materials [20]. The Eco-design Directive aims to ensure the reduction of environmental impacts throughout the life cycle of products while ensuring eco-design, resource efficiency and the environmental performance of energy related products [21]. The Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Directive focuses on promoting eco-design and setting recycling and recovery targets for electrical and electronic waste [22]. The Landfill Directive aims at reducing waste while promoting recycling and recovery [23]. Finally, the energy efficiency directive promotes measure to reduce energy consumption and improve energy efficiency contributing to resource efficiency and circularity [24].

Monitoring frameworks and indicators

To describe and monitor the notion of circular economy various concepts have been developed. The main aim of these monitoring frameworks and indicators is to assess the progress and performance in the transition to a circular economy. Some of the most prominent monitoring frameworks and the indicator sets used in these are described in this subchapter.

One of the ways to describe circular economy models is the Butterfly diagram that is used as a visual representation developed by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation [25]. It consists of two wings each one depicting a different phase of the circular economy process. The left one represents the biological cycle, including strategies such as composting, bio-based materials, and natural processes to regenerate and return materials to the environment. The right one represents the technical cycle, focusing on activities like recycling, remanufacturing, and refurbishing to maintain products, components, and materials in use for as long as possible. The body of the butterfly signifies the product design and innovation, which is a crucial element in creating circular solutions. The butterfly diagram highlights the holistic approach of the circular economy, that aims to minimise waste, extend resource lifespans, and support sustainability across economic, environmental, and social dimensions. The Ellen MacArthur Foundation also developed the Circular Economy System Framework. This framework proposes a systemic approach to the circular economy, emphasizing regenerative design, sharing platforms, and sustainable materials management.

Figure 1: The Butterfly diagram

Source: Ellen MacArthur Foundation, Circular economy systems diagram (February 2019), <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/circular-economy-diagram>

There are also the various Rs strategy concepts ranging from three Rs (3RS) [26], namely reduce, reuse, recycle, to 7Rs [27] that includes rethink, redesign, remanufacture, repair, reduce, reuse, and recycle and 9Rs that include recover, recycle, remanufacture, refurbish, repair, reuse, reduce, redesign, rethink. The

9R framework has been enhanced by the PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency (2017) that defines 10 strategies for circularity, in which also refuse is included. [28].

At the EU level the cornerstone of assessing circular economy is the **Circular Economy Monitoring Framework** [29]. This framework was established in December 2017 by the European Commission and Eurostat, it is part of the Circular Economy Action Plan to monitor the progress towards a circular economy and its direct and indirect benefits at the Member States' level, using available statistical data. The framework aims to provide policymakers and stakeholders with data and indicators to measure the transition from a linear economic model to a circular one. The Circular Economy Monitoring Framework consists of a set of indicators that cover various aspects of the circular economy, including resource use, waste generation, recycling rates, and the adoption of circular business practices. These indicators help to evaluate the efficiency of resource use, the reduction of waste, and the extent to which circular practices are being implemented. This allows the EU and national authorities to assess whether policies are effective and to identify best practices. In addition, it informs European citizens about the impact of EU climate and environmental policies and facilitates knowledge and information exchange among policymakers in different governance levels on where further efforts are needed. Furthermore, these indicators can be used for benchmarking for cities when defining a monitoring framework.

In 2023, the Commission revised the circular economy monitoring framework [30]. The new European Circular Economy Monitoring Framework focuses on aspects of circular economy related to resource use and waste management. It consists of 10 indicators – some of which are broken down into sub-indicators -, across four different dimensions, namely *Production and Consumption*, *Waste Management*, *Secondary Raw Materials*, *Competitiveness*, and *Innovation* are investigated. These indicators were selected to capture the main elements of circular economy, so that the list would be concise. It uses available data while also earmarking areas where new indicators are needed. Aspects relating to green public procurement, food waste, maintaining the value of products and materials for longer – such as design for circularity, repair, reuse, and circular consumption – are not yet included.

Based on the European Commission's circular economy monitoring framework and its key circularity areas, in the methodology developed by the **Cities and Regions Initiative**, over 100 metrics related to early-stage transition of circular systems have been developed [31]. These assessment criteria are subdivided between basic and advanced indicators. Advanced metrics need a complex method or collection process to be calculated, compared to the basic ones simply obtained through statistical data. In relation to more advanced stages of circular transition, selected indicators for circular economy state of implementation have been suggested and provide valuable information about the socio-economic spectrum of an examined city or region, including circularity areas such as awareness/ information campaigns, capacity building, regulation, funding and taxation, policy, industrial symbiosis, and eco-design.

The European Commission has also tried to overcome the issue that a lack of a commonly accepted circular economy definition hinders the circular transition, by proposing a sector agnostic circular economy categorization system [32]. This system defines categories of activities that substantially contribute to circular economy. It includes a guide with an indicative list of typical circular economy projects

or investments. It aims to contribute to the finance aspect of the EU taxonomy with regard to achieving circular economy objectives.

Similarly, the **Resource Efficiency Scoreboard indicators**, an annual publication by the European Environment Agency (EEA) that provides an overview of key resource efficiency indicators for the European Union, illustrates the progress towards increased resource efficiency of individual Member States and the European Union as a whole [33]. The Resource Efficiency Scoreboard is a set of 30 robust and easily understandable indicators for assessing the use of natural resources in the EU and for monitoring the progress towards a resource-efficient and circular economy. The scoreboard includes a lead indicator on resources, dashboard indicators on materials, land, water and carbon, and theme-specific indicators. It shows progress towards resource efficiency in the EU and its Member States. Topic wise, the European Academies' science advisory council finds that many indicators are available which are relevant for the circular economy [34]. These are grouped into sustainable development, environment, material flow analysis, societal behaviour, organisational behaviour, and economic performance.

A general guidance is provided on the criteria for selecting indicators. In addition, a conceptual framework for a Circular Resource Management Roadmap was also developed [35]. In specific, the Urban Agenda Partnership on Circular Economy aims to support urban authorities in implementing a circular resource management plan as part of the transition from waste management to resource management. The partnership aims to stimulate the re-use, repair, refurbishment and recycling of existing materials and products to promote new growth and job opportunities. Urban Agenda Partnerships have been established for several urban priority themes under the EU Urban Agenda, including Circular Economy.

At an international level, the global indicator framework for Sustainable Development Goals and targets of the 2030 agenda for Sustainable Development, was developed by the Inter-Agency and Expert Group on SDG (Sustainable Development Goals) Indicators (**IAEG-SDGs**) [36]. The IAEG-SDGs was tasked to develop and implement the global indicator framework for the Goals and targets of the 2030 Agenda. The global indicator framework was developed by the IAEG-SDGs and agreed upon, including refinements on several indicators, at the 48th session of the United Nations Statistical Commission held in March 2017. The SDG indicators are a framework of indicators and statistical data to monitor progress, inform policy and ensure accountability of all stakeholders. The indicator framework aims to turn the SDGs and their targets into a management tool to help countries develop implementation strategies and allocate resources accordingly, as well as a report card to measure progress towards sustainable development and help ensure the accountability of all stakeholders for achieving the SDGs.

From an academia front, Merino-Saum et.al, investigated circular economy indicator frameworks related to **sustainable cities** [37]. Urban sustainability indicators are important instruments for assessing the performance of cities. They include environmental, economic, and social indicators designed to detect progress in meeting the objectives of sustainability understood in its broadest sense. Specifically, these are tools that allow city planners, city managers and policymakers to gauge the socio-economic and environmental impact of, for example, current urban designs, infrastructures, policies, waste disposal systems, pollution, and access to services by citizens. They allow for the diagnosis of problems and pressures, and thus the identification of areas that would profit from being addressed through good

governance and science-based responses. They also allow cities to monitor the success and impact of sustainability interventions.

All actions that these partners work on are gathered in the Circular Economy Implementation Programme. To be able to track whether that transition is on course, a monitoring system is needed. This report goes beyond the ten indicators proposed by the European Commission, as it systemically maps the current effects and the preconditions for the transition process to achieve the desired effects, over time. It also provides a baseline assessment, in which the indicators provided include the following value chains: biomass and food, manufacturing, construction, plastics, and consumer goods.

At the local level, there is a variety of approaches. One well-known example is **Circular Economy Monitor** for Flanders [38]. It aims to provide an inventory of indicators that are relevant to monitor the transition to a circular economy (CE) and to measure the effects of new policy and trends. More than 100 indicators are divided into different categories, including circularity (e.g., indicators that portray the circularity of the entire economy focusing on inflow, R-strategies and outflow), effects (e.g., materials' footprint, ecological effects on soil and climate, etc.), housing (e.g., footprint of the buildings), food (e.g., impact of consumption and waste streams), consumer goods (e.g., reuse and repair percentage of appliances and furniture) and lastly, mobility (e.g., life cycle of vehicle and citizens' movement).

The Circular Cities indicators set developed within the CityLoops Project also provides a comprehensive set of behavioural, economic, and environmental indicators to assess the transition towards a Circular City. Based on the analysis of the circular transition approaches adopted by 60 cities across Europe, through the European Circular Cities Declaration, CityLoops developed a framework for the transition to a circular economy in urban areas. Such framework (depicted in the figure below) is based on the four core objectives or Vision Elements summarised below:

(Vision Element 1) The local government, civil society, businesses, the research community and other local stakeholders collaborate to promote the transition from a linear to a circular economy. This means in practice:

(Vision Element 2) fostering business models and economic behavioural patterns that maintain the value and utility of products, components, materials and nutrients for as long as sensible, leading to:

(Vision Element 3) closing of material loops and minimising harmful resource use and waste generation locally as much as possible, and thereby:

(Vision element 4) improving human well-being, minimise net environmental impacts, protect and enhance biodiversity, and promote social inclusion, both within the city and globally, in line with the sustainable development goals.

Figure 2: The four vision elements of the circular city vision and causal links for CE transition.
Source: ICLEI Europe

To measure the city's progress towards the circular transition, 97 indicators have been elaborated and grouped according to intermediate strategic objectives that contribute to the achievement of the Vision elements mentioned above. "The indicators are partly process focused (i.e. aiming to document the process and actions carried out by the cities, mostly in the Vision Element 1) and partly impact focused (i.e. evaluating the effect in terms of economic value or changes in material flows, Vision Elements 2 and 3)". Given limited time span and limitations in data availability some indicators related to the Strategic Objectives related to improving human wellbeing and reducing environmental impacts are still being identified.

Circularity indicators play a crucial role in evaluating the potential of initiatives and they can assess the impact and scale of circular economy projects within cities. They can be quantitative and qualitative metrics used to assess the circularity potential of specific initiatives, interventions, or projects. They help in evaluating the extent to which a project aligns with the principles of circular economy, including reducing waste, promoting resource efficiency, and encouraging sustainable practices. These indicators are crucial for guiding decision-making, monitoring progress, and evaluating the impact of circular

economy projects in urban settings. According to Geissdoerfer et al. [39], circularity indicators play a central role in measuring the environmental and economic performance of circular economy projects. They can encompass a range of parameters, such as material flows, energy consumption, greenhouse gas emissions, and resource use efficiency. For instance, indicators related to the use of recycled or upcycled materials in a project can quantify the reduction in virgin resource consumption and associated environmental impacts. Additionally, indicators assessing product design for remanufacturing or refurbishment potential can demonstrate how circular practices can extend the lifespan of products, reducing waste generation. These indicators are essential as they offer valuable insights into the circularity potential and the overall sustainability impact of projects. By evaluating circular economy initiatives at the project scale, cities can identify opportunities to optimise resource use, minimize waste generation, and increase overall environmental performance. Monitoring the progress of circular projects using such indicators allows cities to track their circular economy journey, understand the effectiveness of interventions, and adapt strategies as needed.

Apart from a city perspective, in a product/company scale the **Material Circularity Indicator** (MCI) is prominent as well [40]. The MCI tool, which is part of a broader 'Circular Indicators Project' developed by The Ellen MacArthur Foundation and Grant Design, allows companies to identify additional, circular value from their products and materials, and mitigate risks from material price volatility and material supply. Regardless of where a specific company sits within this supply chain, the MCI calculation provides useful information for assessing, from a perspective beyond its own gates, how circular its product is and what bottlenecks or opportunities there are in its supply chain. The MCI offers insights into material flows for the whole life cycle of a product, using a technique known as a Material Flow Analysis (MFA). The indicator's focus is on Technical Cycles, which encourages more circular design principles from the extraction of raw resources to the construction and eventual demolition stages. It is considered as an extremely useful tool for measuring and improving the circularity of a product. It can help to provide a more comprehensive picture when identifying hotspots in the production process or assessing how a product fits into a project's overall environmental impact.

A conceptual analysis framework for quantifying and analysing the development of the EU Bioeconomy, was conducted by Kardung et. al (2021) [41]. The driving forces and relations within the bioeconomy, how bioeconomy can be defined and how to monitor and measure the bioeconomy with indicators are discussed in this paper. The development of the bioeconomy is proven to be driven by forces such as technology and innovation, market organisation, policies, strategies, and legislation. The identified drivers help to provide indicators to monitor and measure bioeconomy. The proposed indicators are divided into categories, e.g., food and nutrition security, sustainable natural resource management, and employment and economic competitiveness. The identified drivers and indicators can be used by public authorities to steer the developments in the bio-based sectors, to manage their investment plans, and to monitor and evaluate a bankable project in bioeconomy.

The Policy Guide on Circular economy and Territorial Consequences (ESPON EGTC, 2019) aims to inspire local and regional policymakers to develop circular economy (CE) strategies that can change the structure and operations of their economies and industries, so that they can better contribute to more sustainable economic growth in Europe [42]. This interactive guide provides suggestions on how to

assess the local and regional contexts needed to adopt the right policy strategies and targets. It also gives insights on how to choose the right policy strategy, define priority areas, set favourable framework conditions and how to monitor and evaluate the outcomes. Examples are used throughout the guide to illustrate the various elements. An overview of the concept of CE is provided along with actions that should be taken to incorporate CE in a policy landscape, as well as good practices in policymaking. The content in the second part of the report helps cities and regions to set up a comprehensive policy strategy. This starts with assessing the local context and potential for CE, setting the right policy priorities, setting out the governance and implementation processes, and ensuring favourable framework conditions via policy mix. The document presents policy measures which can be particularly useful for cities and regions. Some examples of the suggested measures include providing R&D infrastructure, regulations supporting CE, providing direct funding, and supporting innovation incubators focusing on CE-related areas. Finally, valuable resources are provided such as studies and reports, practical and policy guides, videos, and web platforms. Setting up the right policy objectives and strategy is an important enabler for a successful design, implementation, and uptake of a bankable circular economy project at local/regional level.

Table 1: Summary of the main policies and initiatives.

Title	Scale (local/national/EU/global)	Year	Type (Framework/ Indicator Set)	Description
Delivering the European Green Deal – European Commission [5]	EU	2021	Policy	Outlines the investments needed and the financing tools available and explains how to ensure a just and inclusive transition.
Circular economy action plan [4]	EU	2020	Policy	A comprehensive body of legislative and non-legislative actions aimed to transition the European economy from a linear to a circular economy model.
Bioeconomy strategy [17]	EU	2012	Action Plan	Covers all the sectors and systems that rely on biological resources (animals, plants, microorganisms, and derived biomass, including organic waste), their functions and principles.
Waste Framework Directive [19]	EU	2008	Directive	Prevents and reduces the negative impacts caused by the generation and management of waste and to improve resource efficiency.
Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive [20]	EU	1994	Directive	Includes targets for recycling and recovery of packaging waste and promotes the use of recycled materials in new packaging.

Title	Scale (local/national/EU/global)	Year	Type (Framework/ Indicator Set)	Description
Eco-design Directive [21]	EU	2022	Directive	Sets ecological standards for energy-using and energy-related products.
Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Directive [43].	EU		Directive	Focuses on promoting eco-design and setting recycling and recovery targets for electrical and electronic waste
The Landfill Directive [44].	EU		Directive	Aims at reducing waste while promoting recycling and recovery
Energy efficiency directive [45].	EU		Directive	Promotes measures to reduce energy consumption and improve energy efficiency contributing to resource efficiency and circularity

Table 2: Summary of the main monitoring frameworks and indicator sets.

Title	Scale (local/national/EU/global)	Year	Type (Framework/ Indicator Set)	Description
EU taxonomy for sustainable activities [18]	EU	2023	Framework	An EU-wide classification system for sustainable investment.
The butterfly diagram: visualising the circular economy [25]	Local	2015	Framework	The diagram depicts the circular economy concept and highlights the continuous flow of biological and technical materials through the “value circle”.
Circular economy system framework [8]	Global	2020	Framework	Includes universal circular economy policy goals.
3R framework [26]	EU	2014	Framework	Defines 3 strategies for circularity and includes reduce, reuse and recycle
7R framework [27]	EU	2015	Framework	Defines 7 strategies for circularity and includes, rethink, redesign, remanufacture, repair, reduce, reuse and recycle.
9R Framework [28]	EU	2017	Framework	Defines 9 strategies for circularity, it includes refuse, rethink, reduce, reuse, repair, refurbish, remanufacture, repurpose, recycle, and recover.

Title	Scale (local/national/EU/global)	Year	Type (Framework/ Indicator Set)	Description
European Circular Economy Monitoring Framework [31]	EU	2017	Indicator Set	Focuses on aspects of the circular economy related to resource use and waste management.
Categorisation system for the circular economy [33]	EU	2020	Categorisation system	A sector-agnostic categorisation system for activities substantially contributing to the circular economy
Resource Efficiency Scoreboard indicators [34]	EU	2014	Indicator Set	Illustrates the progress towards increased resource efficiency of individual Member States and the European Union as a whole.
Circular Economy: Indicators and Priorities for Critical Materials – EASAC [35]	EU	2016	Indicator Set	Includes indicators based on sectors i.e., sustainable development, environment, material flow analysis, societal behaviour, organisational behaviour, and economic performance, are addressed.
Urban Agenda Partnership on Circular Economy [36]	EU	2021	Framework	Supports urban authorities in implementing a circular resource management plan as part of the transition from waste management to resource management.
Global indicator framework for Sustainable Development Goals [37]	EU	2017	Indicator Set	Framework of indicators and statistical data to monitor progress, inform policy and ensure accountability of all stakeholders.
Circular Economy Monitor for Flanders [56]	Local	2018	Indicator Set	An inventory of indicators that are relevant to monitor the transition to a circular economy and to measure the effects of new policy and trends.
Material Circularity Indicator [57]	Local	2021	Indicator Set	Allows companies to identify additional, circular value from their products and materials, and mitigate risks from material price volatility and material supply.
Development of the Circular Bioeconomy: Drivers and Indicators [58]	EU	2021	Indicator Set	Proposes indicators that are divided into categories, e.g., food and nutrition security, sustainable natural resource management, and employment and economic competitiveness.

Title	Scale (local/national/EU/global)	Year	Type (Framework/ Indicator Set)	Description
Policy Guide on Circular economy and Territorial Consequences [59]	EU	2019	Framework	Provides suggestions on how to assess the local and regional contexts needed to adopt the right policy strategies and targets.

The DEFINITE-CCRI TIP Evaluation Framework

The DEFINITE-CCRI project developed a flexible and easy to customise framework that will be used to assess how suitable the projects are to advance the EU Green Deal in line with the EU taxonomy, the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, and the European Bioeconomy Strategy, by demonstrating a strong environmental, social and economic impact potential in deploying innovative and systemic circular solutions. The EU monitoring framework for the circular economy, coupled with input from the methodology for implementing a circular economy at the local and regional scale developed by CCRI, as well as indicators stemming from the CityLoops project¹, forms the basis of the indicators used in the DEFINITE-CCRI toolbox.

More particularly, the selection of the indicators used has been initiated mainly according to the 9R strategies and the impact pathways described below, which provided a basis for the development of the assessment procedure. The final selection of indicators and impacts chosen for each the evaluation of each project deviated in part from this approach due to complexity and variety of projects received that could not all be sensibly grasped by the proposed approach. However, framework developed and described below is coherent attempt and has worked as starting point in the TIP evaluation within DEFINITE-CCRI – starting from the 9R strategies - and shaped, eventually, the format of the excel questionnaires that the selected projects would have to fill in with their respective input each. The non-tailored version of these excel questionnaires are included in Annex I.

General approach

Projects submitted to the DEFINITE-CCRI Deal Engine Mechanism and subjected to the Technical Impact Potential (TIP) assessment will be evaluated (1) with regard to their technological readiness, technical state-of-the-art and technological innovation (potential), (2) projects will be evaluated based on their potential to impact positively on environmental domains such as e.g., water, soil and climate, social categories such as e.g., jobs, public health, skill development, inclusion of marginalized groups, consumer awareness etc. and with regard to macro-economic indicators such as e.g., local economy transformation and resilience.

¹ <https://cityloops.metabolismofcities.org/indicators/#ve-1>

In this, the impact potential is understood as the impact the project aims to achieve to positively affect the surrounding system boundary (e.g., the municipality, region, or country) on the outlined environmental, social, and economic impact domains (see table below).

Table 3: Criteria and indicators for the technology and innovation assessment

Criteria	Indicator (formula)	Description/data needs
Technology readiness level	TRL of the technology - Scale from 1 to 9	TRL is a type of measurement system used to assess the maturity level of a particular technology. TRL 1 Basic Principle Observed, TRL 2 Technology concept formulated, TRL3 Experimental proof of concept, TRL 4 Technology validated in lab, TRL 5 Technology validated in relevant environment, TRL 6 Technology demonstrated in relevant environment, TRL 7 System prototype demonstration in operational environment, TRL 8 System complete and qualified, TRL 9 Actual system proven in operational environment
Adoption of circular economy technologies and innovations	The extent to which the project within a region or sector have embraced and integrated practices and technologies associated with the circular economy.	The level of integration of circular economy technologies and innovative practices that support the principles of circular economy. 1 being the approach is not that innovative to 5 the approach is highly innovative and uses state of the art technologies.
Degree of digitalization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation of industry 4.0 technologies for resource efficiency. 	The level of implementation of Industry 4.0 technologies in the market, of IoT technologies, The level of employment of data analytics tools in the market, The level of utilization of smart technologies in the market
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration of IoT and data analytics for production optimization. 	The level of incorporation of Industry 4.0 technologies or of IoT technologies in the production activities. The level of deploying data analytics and relevant tools in the production practices, The level of utilization of smart technologies in the production practices. 1 being no industry 4.0 or IoT technologies and data analytics tool whatsoever, 3 being in some aspects of the production or the approach, and 5 being using IoT technologies and data analytics where applicable.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of data analytics for evidence-based decision-making. 	The level of employment of data analytics tools in the approach, 1 being

Criteria	Indicator (formula)	Description/data needs
		no industry 4.0 or IoT technologies and data analytics tool whatsoever, 3 being in some aspects of the resource management or the approach, and 5 being using IoT technologies and data analytics where applicable.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation of smart technologies for resource management. 	The level of incorporation of Industry 4.0 technologies or of IoT technologies in the resource management activities. The level of deploying data analytics and relevant tools in the resource management practices, The level of utilization of smart technologies in in the resource management practices. 1 being no industry 4.0 or IoT technologies and data analytics tool are used whatsoever, 3 being them used in some aspects of the resource management or the approach, and 5 being using IoT technologies and data analytics where applicable.

Connection with ICLEI's 4-pillar transition model

The TIP framework operationalizes and adapts the four-pillar transition model as well as indicator set [46] developed by ICLEI and partners in the CityLoops project. The 9R-strategies stand for different types of circular business models/behavioural patterns/circular systemic solutions (CCS) and thus represent Pillar 2 of the model. The strategic objectives/targets associated with changes in the biophysical economy (increased circularity) represent pillar 3 of the model, while the environmental, social, and economic impact domains stand for pillar 4 of the transition model.

1. Collaboration between stakeholders for the Circular Transition

2. Improving environmental quality and human well-being

Figure 3: The elements of the DEFINITE CCRI 5 pillar transition model

Impact pathways and project impact assessment

The entry point to the impact potential assessment are the 9R-strategies. Each project will be grouped depending on the 9R-strategies they pertain to. Depending on the 9R-strategy, the associated strategic circularity objectives are being assessed using the pertaining indicators (see table 4). Example: a project working with a solution/idea pertaining mainly to the sharing economy would be grouped to the *Rethink* strategy and thus be evaluated for three strategic circularity objectives/targets - *Reduced material consumption*, *Reduced waste generation* and *Reduced overall energy demand and increased share of renewable energy* (see table 6 below) through the associated KPIs (see table 6). Depending on the strategic circularity objectives/target, specific environmental, social, and economic impacts will be evaluated – e.g., for the objective/target of “Reduced material consumption” it will be *Improved air quality*, *Reduced soil degradation* and *Mitigate climate change* (environmental), *Improved recreational services (social)*, as well as *Increased resilience of local economy and Growth of circular consumer goods markets and startups*.

Figure 4: schematic sketch of impact pathways, source: ICLEI Europe

Table 4: Impact potential assessment framework – strategic circularity objectives or targets per R-strategy

R-strategy (project type)	Strategic circularity objective / target
Refuse (making product redundant by abandoning its function or making a radically different product)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced (harmful) material consumption Reduced waste generation
Rethink (making product use more intensive (e.g. by sharing))	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced material consumption Reduced waste generation Reduced overall energy demand and increased share of renewable energy
Reduce (increasing efficiency in production, using fewer resources)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced material consumption Reduced overall energy demand and increased share of renewable energy

R-strategy (project type)	Strategic circularity objective / target
Reuse (reuse by another consumer of discarded product still with its original function)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced material consumption • Reduced overall energy demand and increased share of renewable energy • Reduced waste generation • Increased quantity of materials available for the next cycle
Repair (repair and maintenance of defective product to restore original function)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced material consumption • Increased self-sufficiency / self-reliance • Reduced waste generation
Refurbishment (restore and old product bringing it up to date)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced overall energy demand and increased share of renewable energy
Remanufacture (Use parts of discarded product in a new product)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced material consumption • Reduced overall energy demand and increased share of renewable energy • Reduced waste generation • Increased quantity of materials available for the next cycle
Repurpose (Use discarded product or its parts in a new product with different function)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced material consumption • Reduced overall energy demand and increased share of renewable energy • Reduced waste generation • Increased quantity of materials available for the next cycle
Recycle (process materials to obtain the same (higher grade) or lower (lower grade) quality)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased share of secondary materials in overall material demand • Increased quantity of materials available for the next cycle • Reduced incineration and landfilling activities and amounts subjected
Recover (incineration of materials with energy recovery)	n.a.

Table 5: Impact potential assessment framework – strategic circularity objectives per impact domain

Strategic circularity objective / target	Environmental impact	Social impact	Economic impact
Reduced (harmful) material consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved air quality Reduced soil degradation Mitigate climate change (indirect) Reduced energy consumption / efficiency (energy per unit output – kWh/€) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved recreational services (indirect) Increased inclusivity and social participation Job creation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased resilience of local economy <i>Growth of circular consumer goods markets and startups</i>
Increased share of renewable and secondary raw materials in overall material demand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved air quality Improved water quality Mitigate climate change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved recreational services (indirect) Improved public health (indirect) Increased inclusivity and social participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased resilience of local economy <i>Contributions to local GDP</i> <i>Growth of circular consumer goods markets and startups</i>
Increased share of secondary materials in overall material demand		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced unemployment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased resilience of local economy <i>Contributions to local GDP</i> <i>Growth of circular consumer goods markets and startups</i>
Increased self-sufficiency / self-reliance			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased resilience of local economy Transformed, sustainable local economy (indirect) <i>Contributions to local GDP</i> <i>Growth of circular consumer goods markets and startups</i>
Increased quantity of materials available for the next cycle	n.a.		

Reduced waste generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved air quality (indirect) Reduced soil (indirect) Improved water quality (indirect) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Increased inclusivity and social participation</i> 	
Reduced incineration and landfilling activities and amounts subjected	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mitigate climate change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved public health 	

Table 6: Impact potential assessment framework – indicators per strategic circularity objectives

Group	Strategic circularity objective/target	Indicators (circularity)
Material/energy flow	Reduced (harmful) raw material consumption	31: Number of kms travelled per year 32: Share of transport that runs on Renewables (bio-CNG, EVs) 33: Increased lifetime of electronics 34: Domestic material consumption (DMC)
	Reduced overall energy demand and increased share of renewable energy	36: Total energy demand 37: Share of renewable energy in total energy demand 38: Local biomass for energy generation 39: Energy efficiency: Total energy consumption/total floor area.
Re-use and recycling	Increased share of renewable and secondary raw materials in overall material demand	26: Waste diversion by reusing electronics 27: Increased share of materials retained and reused on demonstration sites 28: Volume onsite sorting (Improved source separation) 41: Share of renewable raw materials in domestic material consumption 42: Share of secondary materials in domestic material consumption
	Increased self-sufficiency / self-reliance	43: Share of local secondary materials in domestic material consumption 44: Import of materials 46: Export of waste materials to incineration 49: EU self-sufficiency for raw materials 50: Number of items repaired, or number of items received 51: Percentage of circular water inflow 52: Percentage of circular water outflow
	Increased quantity of materials available for the next cycle	27: Increased share of materials retained and reused on demonstration sites 28: Volume onsite sorting (Improved source separation) 29: Total material collected by the project (Stored: material bank/collected (efficiency))

		53: Quantity of material subjected to reuse 54: Quantity of material subjected to repair 55: Quantity of material subjected to remanufacturing 56: Quantity of material subjected to recycling 57: Quantity of material for anaerobic digestion 59: EOL-RR (End of Life Recycling Rate). Specify the share of mass going to landfill, energy recovery, recycling, re-use 60: Quantity of material for composting 63: Water circulation of the wastewater 64: Freshwater use 65: Energy intensity of the operations 66: Energy production/unit of input (ton of feedstock)
Waste generation/management	Reduced waste generation	59: EOL-RR (End of Life Recycling Rate). Specify the share of mass going to landfill, energy recovery, recycling, re-use 68: Incineration rates per material fractions 70: Landfilling rates per material fractions 71: Share of virgin material used plus its composition breakdown.
	Reduced incineration and landfilling activities and amounts subjected	68: Incineration rates per material fractions 70: Landfilling rates per material fractions 72: Treatment of the remaining amounts

Table 7: Impact potential assessment framework – indicators (circularity) metadata

Group	#	Indicator name	Indicator definition	Unit
Material / energy flow	31	Number of kms travelled per year	Measures the amount of kms travelled in a year for the project	Kms / year
	32	Share of transport that runs on Renewables (bio-CNG, EVs)	Measures the percentage of the transport means used, running on RES	%
	33	Increased lifetime of electronics	Measures how much longer an item is operational	Time in years
Material / energy flow	34	Domestic material consumption (DMC)	The total amount of materials directly used by an economy and is defined as the annual quantity of raw materials extracted from the domestic territory, plus all physical imports minus all physical exports. ^[1]	Tonnes/year
	35	Domestic material consumption (DMC) of virgin materials	The total amount of virgin materials directly used.	Tonnes/year
	36	Total energy demand	Total energy demand for all sectors in the city.	MWh/year
	37	Share of renewable energy in total energy demand	Renewable energy usage in the city as a share of total energy demand	%
	38	Local biomass for energy generation.	Give an overview of local biomass used for energy production (e.g. incineration, biogas).	Tonnes/year

	39	Energy efficiency: Total energy consumption/total floor area.	Measures the total energy consumption per total floor area.	kWh/m ²
Re-use and recycling	40	Circular Material Use Rate	<p>The circular material use rate (CMU), also called Circularity rate measures, in percentage, the share of material recovered and fed back into the economy - thus saving extraction of primary raw materials - in overall material use.</p> <p>A higher Circularity rate value indicates more secondary materials substituting for primary raw materials i.e. avoiding the environmental impacts of extracting primary material.</p>	%
	41	Share of renewable raw materials in domestic material consumption	This indicator assesses the significance of renewable materials in the economy, i.e. resources that have a natural rate of availability and yield a continual flow of services which may be consumed in any time period without endangering future consumption possibilities as long as current use does not exceed net renewal during the period under consideration.	%
	42	Share of secondary materials in domestic material consumption	This indicator assesses the significance of secondary materials in the economy	%
	43	Share of local secondary materials in domestic material consumption	This indicator assesses the significance of locally sourced secondary materials in the economy	%
	44	Import of materials	Identify mass of materials imported at city and sector level	Tonnes/year
	45	Export of waste materials	Identify collected waste at city and sector level being exported out of the city.	Tonnes/year
	46	Export of waste materials to incineration	Assess the share of the waste exported out of the city that goes to incineration	Tonnes/year
	47	Export of waste materials to landfill	Assess the share of the waste exported out of the city that goes to landfill	Tonnes/year
	48	Export of waste materials to composting	Assess the share of the waste exported out of the city that goes to composting	Tonnes/year
		49	EU self-sufficiency for raw materials ^[2]	The indicator measures how much the city is independent from the rest of the world for several raw materials.
	50	Number of items repaired, or number of items received	The indicator measures how many items are being repaired.	Tonnes/year
	51	Percentage of circular water inflow	$Q \text{ total circular water use} / Q \text{ total water use} * 100\%$	%
	52	Percentage of circular water outflow	$Q \text{ total circular water discharge} / Q \text{ total water discharge} * 100\%$	%

	53	Quantity of material subjected to reuse	Estimate mass of materials being reused at city/sector level. "Reuse" means reuse of discarded yet still usable product, for the same purpose, by a different user. ^[3]	Tonnes/year
	54	Quantity of material subjected to repair	Estimate mass of materials being repaired at city/sector level. "Repair" means repair or maintenance of broken or malfunctioning product, to enable continuation of its original function. ⁶	Tonnes/year
	55	Quantity of material subjected to remanufacturing	Estimate mass of materials being remanufactured at city/sector level. 'Remanufacture' means using parts of a discarded product in a new product of the same function. ⁶	Tonnes/year
	56	Quantity of material subjected to recycling	Estimate material subjected to recycling at demo, sector, and city level. "Recycling" means processing of materials to achieve the original high-quality or reduce to low quality. ⁶	Tonnes/year
	57	Quantity of material for anaerobic digestion	Estimate mass of materials going to anaerobic digestion.	Tonnes/year
	58	End of Life Collection Rate	The End-of-Life Collection Rate (EoL CR) measures the efficiency with which end-of-life material fraction is collected.	%
	59	EOL-RR (End of Life Recycling Rate).	The End-of-Life Recycling Rate (EoL RR) measures the efficiency with which the mass contained in End-of-Life products is collected, pre-treated, and finally recycled.	%
	60	Quantity of material for composting	Estimate mass of materials going to composting at demo, sector, and city scale.	Tonnes/year
Waste generation / management	61	Amount of sector specific waste that is produced	Total mass of waste for sector.	Tonnes/year
	62	End of Life Processing Rate	The End-of-Life Processing Rate (EoL PR) measures the efficiency of the end-of-life processing process.	%
	63	Water circulation of the wastewater	Total mass of water used in circulation of wastewater	Tonnes/year
	64	Freshwater use	Total mass of freshwater used.	Tonnes/year
	65	Energy intensity of the operations	Measures the efficiency: energy used per operational output.	Unit of output (kWh) / production unit
	66	Energy production/unit of input (ton of feedstock)	Measures the energy produced per ton of input material.	Unit of output (kWh) / ton of feedstock

	67	Incineration rate	Mass percentage of waste which incinerated.	%
	68	Incineration rates per material fractions	Mass percentage of waste which incinerated for each material fraction as defined by local waste management companies.	%
	69	Landfilling rate	Mass percentage of waste which landfilled.	%
	70	Landfilling rates per material fractions	Mass percentage of waste which landfilled for each material fraction as defined by local waste management companies.	%
	71	Share of virgin material used plus its composition breakdown.	Percentage of new material used plus its composition breakdown.	% per material
	72	Treatment of the remaining amounts	Mass percentage of waste which isn't landfilled or incinerated and how it is treated.	% per types of treatment

Table 8: Impact potential assessment framework – indicators per impact domain

Group	Impact	Indicators (impact)
Well-being	Improved education	73: Percentage of school-aged population enrolled in school
		74: Percentage of students completing secondary education
	Improved public health	75: Average life expectancy
		76: Number of in-patient hospital beds per 100,000 population
	Improved recreational services	77: Open green space area ratio per 100,000 inhabitants
		78: Share of green space areas within urban limits
	Improved access to basic services	79: Percentage of city population with potable water supply service
80: Percentage of city population with authorized electrical service		
81: Percentage of city population with regular solid waste collection (residential)		
82: Percentage of city population served by wastewater collection		
Reduced unemployment	30: CE-based employment: Number of new CE related jobs and number of existing jobs becoming circular	
	83: Unemployment rate	
Reduced poverty and inequality	84: AROP – at-risk-of-poverty rate for the total population	
	85: QSR – income quintile share ratio.	

	Human-centred land-use and urban planning	86: Average commuting distance/time 87: Share of population having access to public transport within 15 minutes by foot 88: Percentage of urban development that occurs on existing urban land rather than on greenfield land
	<i>Improved inclusivity and social participation</i>	
Environment impacts (local)	Biodiversity loss and deforestation	89: Percentage of city area protected as natural sites
	Improved water quality	90: Percentage of residential and commercial wastewater that is treated according to applicable national standards 91: Percentage of water samples in a year that comply with national potable water quality standards
	Improved air quality	92: Urban population exposure to air pollution by particulate matter 93: Levels of Particulate Matter (PM10 – mg/m3) 94: Levels of Particulate Matter (PM2.5 – mg/m3)
	Reduced soil degradation	60: Quantity of material for composting
Environment impacts (global)	Mitigate climate change	95: GHG emissions per year 96: Annual CO2 equivalent emissions per capita 97: Annual CO2 emissions per unit of GDP
	Reduce global adverse environmental impact of local consumption	
Economic impacts	Transformed, sustainable local economy	
	<i>Contribution to local GDP</i>	
	<i>Growth of circular consumer goods markets and startups</i>	
	Increased resilience of local economy	
Impacts on urban resilience	Reduced risk of urban infrastructure against natural disasters	

Table 9: Impact potential assessment framework – indicators (impact) metadata

Group	#	Indicator name	Indicator definition	Unit
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Well-being	73	Percentage of school-aged population enrolled in school	Percentage of school-aged population enrolled in school	%
	74	Percentage of students completing secondary education	Percentage of students completing secondary education	%
	75	Average life expectancy	Average life expectancy	Years
	76	Number of in-patient hospital beds per 100 000 population	Number of in-patient hospital beds per 100,000 population	Beds / 100,000 inhabitants
	77	Open green space area ratio per 100,000 inhabitants	Open green space area ratio per 100,000 inhabitants	Hectare / 100,000 people
	78	Share of green space areas within urban limits	Share of green space areas within urban limits	%
	79	Percentage of city population with potable water supply service	Total houses connected to potable water supply service. Total inhabitants living in these houses.	%
	80	Percentage of city population with authorized electrical service	Total houses connected to electrical service/ infrastructure. Total inhabitants living in these houses.	%
	81	Percentage of city population with regular solid waste collection (residential)	Total houses getting regular waste management service. Total inhabitants living in these houses.	%
	82	Percentage of city population served by wastewater collection	Total amount of houses connected to wastewater sewage works. Total inhabitants living in these houses.	%
	83	Unemployment rate	Eurostat: Unemployed persons are all persons 15 to 74 years of age (16 to 74 years in ES, IT and the UK) who were not employed during the reference week, had actively sought work during the past four weeks and were ready to begin working immediately or within two weeks.	%
	84	AROP – at-risk-of-poverty rate for the total population	Eurostat definition: At risk-of-poverty are persons with an equivalised disposable income below the risk-of-poverty threshold, which is set at 60 % of the national median equivalised disposable income (after social transfers).	%
	85	QSR – income quintile share ratio.	Eurostat: The income quintile share ratio or the S80/S20 ratio is a measure of the inequality of income distribution.	Income ratio

	86	Average commuting distance/time	Average duration of commute (and/or commuting distance) to and from work or an educational establishment, using any types of transport modes.	Time Distance
	87	Share of population having access to public transport within 15 minutes by foot	Population residing <500 metres from a public transport stop (%). ^[1]	%
	88	Percentage of urban development that occurs on existing urban land rather than on greenfield land	Greenfield land can be understood as undeveloped land in a city or rural area either used for agriculture or landscape design or left to evolve naturally. Using the CORINE Land Cover (CLC) nomenclature, ^[2] "existing urban land" would be all areas in the Area class "Artificial surfaces" except Area class "141 Green urban areas".	%
Environmental impacts (local)	89	Percentage of city area protected as natural sites	A protected area is a defined geographical space, recognised, dedicated, and managed, through legal or other effective means, to achieve the long-term conservation of nature with associated ecosystem services and cultural values. (IUCN Definition 2008)	%
	90	Percentage of residential and commercial wastewater that is treated according to applicable national standards	Wastewater treatment is the process of removing suspended and dissolved physical, chemical, and biological contaminants to produce (a) water that is safe to be discharged to the environment or suitable for reuse and (b) a solid sludge suitable for disposal or reuse.	%
	91	Percentage of water samples in a year that comply with national potable water quality standards	Number of water samples with in national potable water quality standards.	%

Operational aspects and workflow

The DEFINITE-CCRI consortium partners will develop a data collection template which will be disseminate to project owner with the aim to define the **baseline values** for both the circularity and the impact indicators for the given system boundary (district, municipality, city or region). Through desk research, the consortium will identify benchmark values for each indicator in order to support the performance evaluation of a given project with regard to circularity and impact, using local data, or if not possible, national statistics that can be scaled down using population or GDP (see chapter on baselining methodology below). In particular, the indicators have been developed in a way that will enable the DEFINITE-CCRI consortium partners to evaluate the selected projects on circularity, the technology readiness level, as well as on their environmental, social and macro-economic impact or/and potential impact. Furthermore, as part of the data collection template, project owners will be asked to provide **target values** for

both circularity and associated impact indicators determined to pertain to their project, or for additional impacts the project aims to achieve. Additionally, when necessary and in case of lack of the necessary quantitative data, the project owners shall be asked to provide input on a complementary qualitative questionnaire, also tailored per particular project. Using both data points, the DEFINITE-CCRI consortium will then **calculate and visualize the impact potential** for each impact domain using, where sensible, benchmark scorings developed through literature research as well as through expert judgement.

Furthermore, the following **operational principles** apply for the impact assessment:

- At least one circularity objective has to be evaluated per 9R-strategy. This objective can correspond to more than one indicators. If projects refer to more than one 9R strategy, more than one circularity objectives will need to be evaluated.
- At least one indicator assessing the impact per domain (i.e., environmental, social, macro-economic) needs to be addressed (if applicable), so a minimum of three impact indicators in total for the impact potential.
- The data collection questionnaire needs to be tailored specifically to each project's nature. One excel file with all the potential data inquires can be found in the Annex.
- The consortium will provide the project owners with a recommendation of which impacts, indicators to choose according to the main activities of the project.

Baseline and benchmark methodologies

There are three levels of results per project:

- Project level: the selected indicators per project will be calculated based on information provided by the project owners.
- Baseline (Threshold) per project: an assessment of the baseline per indicator to enable us to assess the technology and impact potential.
- Benchmark per project: looking into similar projects or initiatives and technologies to assess whether the indicators can be improved in the future.

To fully understand the impact and technical potential of the projects all three levels will be investigated.

Benchmark Methodology

A set of quantifiable indicators is associated with each of the 9R-strategies. Each project is requested to report on the relevant indicators, taking TRL into account. For each of the circularity indicators, a benchmark is computed. In contrast with the bottom-up data collection regarding the project impact assessment, in order to compute the benchmarks, a top-down approach using publicly available data is needed.

Ideally, we would prefer to compute a city or industry benchmark, and then defer to a national average if the data to compute at the city or industry level is not available, and lastly defer to a global average if no other data is available. Industry benchmarks can be computed at either the global or national level

depending on data availability, are likely to be less available than geographical benchmarks but are generally preferred.

For each circularity indicator, the project can be benchmarked against the different benchmarks at various levels of detail, depending on the data availability.

See example below: a benchmark may indicate that a project has a high impact relative to the global industry, if that benchmark exists, but a relatively low impact for the country:

Indicator	Project Level	Industry Level	Country Level
Circular Material Use Rate	19%	2%	24%

The benchmarks are intended to frame the impact of projects, not necessarily to compare projects. The projects differ in the type of materials they handle, and their handling methods, their TRL, and their infrastructure. Therefore, additional indicators and information need to be taken into consideration when comparing project indicators.

The benchmark calculation should be standardized and scalable so that it can be used as a benchmark no matter where a project is located.

For each indicator, for each region, we will investigate the availability of local/industry data to create city or industry benchmarks. We have already done a feasibility study of the indicators to determine the most likely level of calculation. For instance, as an example, see the review on the Circular Material Use Rate below.

Circular Material Use Rate: CMUR is defined in Eurostat as the amount of waste recycled in domestic recovery plants minus imported waste destined for recovery plus exported waste destined for recovery abroad.

Waste recycled in domestic recovery plants comprises the recovery operations R2 to R11 - as defined in the Waste Framework Directive 75/442/EEC.

The imports and exports of waste destined for recycling - i.e. the amount of imported and exported waste bound for recovery – are approximated from the European statistics on international trade in goods.

Information about traded waste and treatment destinations is typically available at the national level. This can be incongruent with city characteristics of waste handling, especially considering the point about incomplete commercial and industrial waste data.

Note that that these limitations apply to indicators related to volume and treatment type of exported waste (i.e. Export of waste materials, Export of waste materials to composting, Export of waste materials to incineration, Export of waste materials to landfill)

Feasibility to calculate:

National level: readily available on Eurostat

Regional level: requires regional data and bespoke calculations but is possible + valuable. Data is required about traded waste, waste volumes and treatment types, as well as detailed household and government expenditure surveys to adequately/reliably scale down consumption (denominator).
City level: very complicated and expensive to measure accurately

Baseline methodology

The project's development is highly based on the assessment of the indicators set for each one of the selected projects on objectives related to the technology used by each shortlisted project receiving PDA Support, to the environmental, social, and micro-economic impact of each, as well as to the level of circularity implemented in each. In that sense, the results deriving from the Operators of the Projects on each set of indicators are going to be scored and benchmarked in the ways necessary to ensure the progress of the selected projects on their technology readiness level, their circularity degree and their impacts on environmental, social and micro-economic issues.

The methods to be used for the benchmarking system of the project shall include both quantitative and qualitative means. The quantitative method shall be implementing in scoring the indicators regarding the environmental, social, micro-economic and circularity impacts in ways that shall allow the assessment of a specific project's contribution in a city-wide level as enough or not. For the implementation of this type of scoring, a baseline shall be set for each indicator which is going to showcase that if a project's impact surpasses it, the project's contribution is respectively positive. The level of the project's contribution shall be respective to where its impact is estimated in regards with the baseline in place.

Further, the qualitative method of scoring shall be used for the indicators regarding the technology readiness of each selected project and will showcase at what degree the specific project's impact has contributed on the objectives examined. This way, the results of each selected project will indicate the levels at which it has progressed on the adoption of circular economy technologies and innovations, the implementation of Industry 4.0 technologies to enhance resource efficiency, the integration of IoT and data analytics, as well as the use of smart technologies to facilitate resources management. The qualitative method of benchmarking shall be implemented by a 1-9 or 1-5 scale measurement that will present the level of progress on each indicator.

In total, considering the broad prism that the indicators used concern, when it comes to assessing the progress on these based on the current benchmarking system, an extensive and in-depth literature review, concerning each of the indicators, will take place. Thus, the desk research done for every indicator affecting the objectives set on environmental, social, micro-economic impacts, the circularity-level and

the technology readiness level of the selected projects, shall allow a reliable and realistic assessment of the progress these projects make and their contribution city-wide.

Process and timeline of the TIP

In this subchapter the step wise approach in implementing the TIP assessment for the circular economy projects is described. Initially, the DEFINITE-CCRI project will select the potential projects that will undertake the PDA. A kick-off meeting with the project owners will take place in September 2023 (M10). Then the FIB and TIP assessments will get initiated. The process of the FIB assessment is described in detail in D3.1. The step wise approach that will be followed for the TIP assessment is presented below. It is worth noting that the FIB and TIP assessments go hand in hand where applicable.

In general, the process of the TIP assessment is mainly based on the data input each of the selected projects are expected to provide, filling out particular and tailored per project questionnaires send out to them. The excel sheets (Annex I) used to create these forms are based on the 9R strategies, as analysed in prior section and include the key indicators linked to each of these 9R strategies, always in accordance with each project's particular scope.

The excels, include sections for data input categorized by the type of circularity indicators necessary to be evaluated. Indicatively, information on the use of material and the overall material input is requested, as well as information on the solid waste, the water use, and the energy consumption factors regarding the overall operation of each project, are needed. This way, the projects are enabled to provide information that the DEFINITE-CCRI Consortium can use to calculate the progress of the projects under assessment on specific, important indicators and to support them during the framework's next and crucial for the viability of their ideas, stage.

Step 1: Setting up the team. The first step is to review the personnel that is already involved in the project. This step ensures that the main roles that need to be included in the project to provide the necessary data and support in the technical and impact related components are covered and to bring forward potential gaps. The engagement of the team as a whole in the TIP assessment ensures that all aspects of the technical and impact potential of the project are addressed and monitored. Establishing a strong link between the DEFINITE-CCRI TIP team and the project team can ensure fruitful cooperation over the TIP support and beyond.

Step 2: Defining the scope of the TIP assessment. The second step of the TIP assessment is to define the scope, outlining the project specific technical and impact components. The DEFINITE-CCRI toolbox has taken into consideration that circular economy projects can vastly vary. This step ensures that the technical and characteristics of the project's approach are being taken into account. During this step we will also look into who needs to be engaged, either coming from the project team, or from the city, or from any other stakeholder, in order to provide the necessary data and information both for the impact and the technical aspects. Steps 1 and 2 will take place in parallel and should not exceed 1 month after the kick-off meeting.

It is worth mentioning that to ensure confidentiality, data protection, and the smooth data exchange between each of the projects that will be assessed and the DEFINITE-CCRI TIP team the possibility of

signing an NDA (Non-Disclosure Agreement) will be investigated. This can be done in collaboration with the FIB assessment as outlined in D3.1 too.

Step 3: Understanding the full scope of the technical and impact components of the project. One of the critical steps in the TIP assessment is to understand the technical solutions included in the project and the potential impact it strives to achieve in a circular, environmental, social, and macro-economic level. To do so, we will delve into the technical characteristics, or the innovations employed within the project, the environmental aspects, how the project interacts with its stakeholders, the social aspects and how it will affect the city in a macro-economic level. To prepare for this step a questionnaire has been prepared and shall be sent out to each project. An outline of the questionnaire can be found in Annex I. The data requests can change and be adjusted depending on the nature and scope of each project. This step will happen simultaneously with Step 3 of the FIB assessment. Since the information needed is extensive and some feedback rounds may also need to take place between the projects and the DEFINITE-CCRI TIP team, this step is expected to take 3 to 4 months to be completed for all the projects, the latest that this step needs to be completed is by February 2024 (M16).

Step 4: TIP introduction. During this stage which is planned to take place in parallel to the Step 3, the DEFINITE-CCRI TIP team is going to provide short TIP introduction meetings to each of the projects' owners in order to make the process and the expected results more clear to them. These calls shall be part of the FIB calls with each project separately and last for about 10 minutes at the end of each FIB call.

Step 5: Send out the questionnaires. At this stage, following the introductory calls, the DEFINITE-CCRI TIP team is expected to send out the excel questionnaires - as already described and included in Annex I - in a way that the data requests are tailored according to the scope and nature of each of the projects under assessment.

Step 6: Open door calls. After sending out the TIP excels on data input, the DEFINITE-CCRI TIP team will ensure to make themselves available for an hour-long slot every week for a month, so that the project owners can have the opportunity to communicate directly with the TIP team and ask guidance or clarifications on filling out the excels.

Step 7: Complementary communication. During this step, following the guidance to the projects in order to fill out the TIP excels, the DEFINITE-CCRI TIP team shall hold additional meetings with each project when ad hoc necessary – mainly in lack of concrete input for the TIP data excels. In these meetings, the projects shall be interviewed and ask to provide input on additional, open end and qualitative questions to clarify as much as possible regarding their processes, approach, and impact potential.

Step 8: Collecting and assessing data: In parallel with the previous steps, the TIP team will implement the DEFINITE-CCRI framework and will start analysing and developing the necessary qualitative and quantitative indicators to calculate the performance of the projects using publicly available data, where applicable, along with the data provided by the projects, while also using some of the tools and services described above. In this step the potential gaps in data and information will be identified and their bridging will be attempted using the qualitative input of the projects. In this step, any subcontracting needs for data provision or any other requirements by the project owners or local stakeholders will emerge.

The subcontracting needs for each project will be looked into within task 4.2.1 and will be reported in D4.2.

Step 9: Additional input. In this step, based on the gaps identified – where identified – during the previous stage, the TIP team may reach out again to the projects in order to ask for additional information, when considered necessary.

Step10: Reporting on the Technical and Impact potential assessment for every project. Once the DEFINITE-CCRI framework has been implemented with the data collected and assessed in steps 4-9 a baseline report will be generated for each project. This report will outline the technical and impact potential for each project and will provide insights that will be useful for the Due Diligence phase. Each report will include the project information, the technical characteristics, and the impact potential by presenting the results of the DEFINITE-CCRI framework, any assumptions that were used or limitations in calculating the indicators and the required next steps to prepare for the project appraisal in the due diligence phase. The final report needs to be concise and easy to read so it will be short (i.e., approximately 10 pages) and will be standardized, containing similar (where applicable) information for all the projects. The reports for each of the projects will be delivered in March/ April 2024 (M17 and 18) to support the decision for the project appraisal and to provide feedback to the projects in a timely manner, as well as to discuss with the owners further when needed. In the figure below the GANTT chart for the ten steps of the TIP assessment is presented. It is worth mentioning that the TIP and FIB have been set up on similar timelines.

Table 610: TIP timeline

DEFINITE-CCRI Work Months	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18
STEP 1 Setting up the team									
STEP 2 Defining the scope of the TIP assessment									
STEP 3 Understanding the full scope of the technical and impact components of the project									
STEP 4 TIP introduction									
STEP 5 Send out the questionnaires									
STEP 6 Open door calls									
STEP 7 Complementary communication									

STEP 8 Collecting and assessing data									
STEP 9 Additional input									
STEP 10 Reporting on the Technical and Impact potential assessment for every project									
Bilateral exchange with each project on the outcomes of the TIP report									

Technical due diligence support package and process of project appraisal

In the due diligence phase, project owners will receive in-depth technical support with at least one two-day intensive onsite consultation session. Additionally, ad-hoc support will be provided when requested by project owners in written fashion or through virtual meetings. The support proceedings and results for each technical due diligence phase will be reported after the completion of this process. In this chapter the specific services that will be provided to the projects are presented along with a timeline.

After the completion of the TIP assessment some of the projects will go through the due diligence support package. This section aims to outline the range of services that will be made available to the 4 to 6 shortlisted projects between months 14 and 24 of the DEFINITE-CCRI project. During this phase certain action points will be proposed to the projects aiming at further enhancing their impact. The action points will be complemented with services that will be provided to the projects enabling them to uptake the actions. The action points will be given in 3 different short reports including a feasibility study, a technology road mapping exercise, and how to effectively map and engage with the stakeholders.

An integral part of this support involves conducting four two-day onsite bilateral consultation sessions, fostering close collaboration between the technical consortium partners and project owners and their partners as needed. These sessions are designed to facilitate the development of the set of actions for the projects, that will enhance their impact and outreach and are crucial for their eventual appraisal in WP5.

Detailing the Technical Due Diligence Support

The Due Diligence Support encompasses the core of the assistance that projects will receive by the consortium. While Task 4.2 is mainly focused on retrieving the required information, including some iterations with the project owners, so that the indicators that have been selected can be assessed along with the impact of the project, this section details the hands-on assistance and set of actions that will be provided to the projects in the due diligence phase.

Additionally, while the TIP assessment is subdivided in key steps whose timelines can be followed by all the project teams at the same time, the technical Due Diligence Support offers a much more ad-hoc set of services, which can be fulfilled using an on-demand approach.

This document sets out the key blocks of assistance, which will be conducted in parallel and with adjustable timelines for the different projects based on their needs. The offered assistance can be split in three categories based on the types of services that can be accessed, as it is described below. The categories are a feasibility study, technology road mapping exercise, and mapping and engaging with the stakeholders.

Feasibility study

A feasibility study in the context of a technical due diligence process with the aim of enhancing the impact of circular economy projects involves a comprehensive assessment to determine whether the

proposed circular economy project is technically, circularly, and environmentally viable. This study will occur after the initial Technical and Impact Potential Assessment and will be built upon the indicators that were used to evaluate the project's potential.

The feasibility study will include an introduction with background information on the circular economy project and its goals, an explanation of the research methods and data sources used in the study, including how the indicators from the Technical and Impact Potential Assessment can be used, there will be a section on the **technical feasibility** of the project, assessing the TRL of key technologies and innovations, an analysis of the project design, infrastructure requirements, and technology stack, an evaluation of the available resources (raw materials, energy, etc.), an examination of any potential risks or challenges. Following the technical assessment, a **circularity and environmental impact** assessment can take place that will build on the results of the TIP assessment and depending on the project's nature can include the circular material use rate, or the carbon footprint and GHG emissions, etc. Then the **operational feasibility** will be looked into by evaluating the operational processes and workflow, the supply chain management, the capacity and scalability considerations, and the circular economy implementation strategies. Furthermore, a **market analysis** can also be conducted as part of the feasibility plan, including the potential market size and growth, the segmentation, the trends, a competitive analysis, and a SWOT analysis. Potential **risks** will be identified and assessed along with technical challenges that can impact the project's success. This analysis will be complemented by **mitigation strategies**. Finally, an analysis of the **stakeholder engagement** and the partnerships that can benefit the project's impact will be undertaken. The feasibility report will be concluded with a set of **clear and actionable recommendations** for optimizing the circular economy project, enhancing its impact, and mitigating identified risks.

A technology road mapping exercise

A technology road mapping exercise for each circular economy project will be conducted after the feasibility study. It will work as a strategic planning process that aims to define the technological development path and milestones for the project. The main aim is to ensure that the project stays aligned with its objectives and takes advantage of emerging technologies and innovations. The main areas that will be covered in the road mapping exercise are detailed below.

1. Define the Scope and Objectives

Clearly define the scope of the technology road mapping exercise, including the specific technologies and innovations relevant to the circular economy project's goals and objectives.

2. Stakeholder Involvement

Engage key stakeholders, including technical experts, project managers, researchers, and industry partners, in the road mapping process.

3. Current Technology Assessment

Evaluate the current state of technology and innovation within the project using the indicators from the TIP assessment as well as considering the technologies used in material sourcing, production, and waste management, the technological strengths and weaknesses identified during the feasibility study, the existing circular economy practices, and initiatives.

4. Identification of Technological Gaps:

Identify gaps between the current technology state and the desired state for the project's objectives, building on the baseline and benchmark methodologies of the TIP assessment.

5. Technology Trends and Emerging Innovations

Research and analyze technology trends and emerging innovations related to circular economy practices, sustainability, and relevant industries.

6. Goal Setting

Define specific technological goals and objectives that align with the circular economy project's mission and vision. These goals should address identified gaps and leverage emerging technologies.

7. Roadmap Development

Create a technology roadmap that outlines key technological milestones and phases, a timeline for technology adoption and implementation, the identification of critical technologies and innovations, dependencies between different technologies and innovations, metrics, and performance indicators for tracking progress.

8. Prioritization and Resource Allocation

Prioritize technologies and innovations based on their potential impact, feasibility, and alignment with project objectives. Allocate resources, including budget, personnel, and research efforts, to support technology development and adoption.

9. Risk Assessment

Identify potential risks and challenges associated with technology adoption, including technical, regulatory, and market-related risks. Develop mitigation strategies for addressing these risks.

10. Collaboration and Partnerships

Explore opportunities for collaboration with research institutions, industry partners, and technology providers to accelerate technology development and implementation. This can be coupled with the stakeholder mapping and engagement exercise.

11. Monitoring and Review:

Establish a system for monitoring progress, tracking key performance indicators, and reviewing the technology roadmap regularly. Make adjustments to the roadmap as needed based on evolving technologies and project developments.

12. Integration with Project Planning

Integrate the technology roadmap with the overall project planning and execution to ensure seamless implementation of technological advancements.

A well-executed technology road mapping exercise can ensure that the project remains at the forefront of technological innovation and sustainability enabling to adapt to changing technological landscapes and achieve its circular economy objectives effectively.

Mapping the stakeholders and developing an engagement strategy

Mapping stakeholders for a circular economy project involves identifying and analyzing individuals, groups, organizations, and entities that have an interest in or can be influenced by the project. The goal is to understand their interests, needs, concerns, and roles in order to develop an effective stakeholder engagement strategy. Below a detailed overview of the steps involved in stakeholder mapping and how it informs the development of a stakeholder engagement strategy is described.

1. Identify Stakeholders

Initially all potential stakeholders who are relevant to the circular economy project will be listed. This can include individuals, groups, and entities at the local, regional, and national levels. Stakeholders may include:

- Government Agencies: Such as environmental authorities, regulators, and local municipalities.
- Community Members: Including residents, businesses, and community organizations.
- Industry Partners: Such as suppliers, manufacturers, and distributors.
- NGOs and Environmental Groups: Those with an interest in sustainability and circular economy initiatives.
- Academic Institutions: Researchers and educational institutions focused on related fields.
- Investors and Financial Institutions: Including those providing funding or financial support.
- Consumers and Customers: Those who purchase products or services from the project.
- Media and Public Relations: Entities that may influence public perception and awareness.

2. Categorize Stakeholders

Then the stakeholders will be grouped into categories based on their level of interest and influence in the project. This will result in the **interest influence stakeholder matrix**. In this matrix in the upper right corner are key stakeholders of high interest and high influence that need to be engaged closely and have significant influence over the project results. In the lower right corner are stakeholders of high interest and low influence, they need to be informed and shown consideration as well as seek their input where relevant. In the upper left corner are the stakeholders with high influence but low interest, they need to

be addressed and monitor their concerns. Finally, in the lower left corner are stakeholders with low interest and influence, with them basic communication needs to be held but there is not the need to allocate extensive resources.

3. Analyze Stakeholder Interests and Expectations

Research will be conducted to understand the interests, expectations, concerns, and motivations of each stakeholder group. This may involve a focus group, public consultations, and reviewing past interactions.

4. Assess Stakeholder Power and Influence

The level of power and influence each stakeholder wields will be determined. Consider factors like financial resources, regulatory authority, public support, and access to media.

5. Identify Key Issues and Concerns

The key issues, topics, or challenges that are important to each stakeholder group will be identified. Understanding their priorities helps tailor engagement strategies.

6. Develop a Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

Based on the stakeholder mapping and analysis, a comprehensive stakeholder engagement strategy that outlines how the project will interact with and involve each stakeholder group will be drafted. Key elements of the strategy may include:

- Objectives, clearly defined goals for stakeholder engagement.
- Communication Channels, the methods, and channels through which the project will communicate with stakeholders.
- Frequency, how often engagement activities will occur.
- Content and Messaging, tailored messages and information for each stakeholder group.
- Roles and Responsibilities, clearly defined roles for project team members and stakeholders in the engagement process.
- Feedback Mechanisms, ways for stakeholders to provide input, raise concerns, and offer suggestions.
- Conflict Resolution, a process for addressing conflicts or disagreements.
- Monitoring and Evaluation, methods for tracking the effectiveness of engagement efforts.

7. Implement and Adapt the Strategy

The stakeholder engagement strategy will be put into action, and adapted if needed based on feedback, changing circumstances, and evolving stakeholder dynamics.

8. Evaluate and Report and maintain transparency

Continuously evaluate the effectiveness of stakeholder engagement efforts and report on outcomes and progress in project reports and assessments. Ensure transparency in all interactions with stakeholders to build trust and credibility.

Effective stakeholder mapping and that can result in an engagement strategy are essential for garnering support, minimizing conflicts, and aligning the circular economy project with the interests and expectations of the communities and organizations it impacts. It helps create a collaborative and mutually beneficial relationship between the project and its stakeholders.

Impact Potential

Another key set of services will centre around the calculation of relevant impacts of the project (i.e. climate, social, macro-economic). The exact scope will depend largely on the projects selected and the relevant financier from the DEFINITE-CCRI investor base but will surely need to include Life-Cycle-Assessment (LCA), carbon footprinting, material footprinting and indicators related to Economy-wide Material-Flow-Analysis (EW-MFA). The delivery of these services may include the purchase of software or the use of sub-contracts, as needed.

Bilateral consultation session

As clearly laid out in the grant agreement, a key element of the DEFINITE-CCRI value proposition is the possibility of accessing financial, technical, and legal experts for extensive periods of time. In particular, the 2-day bilateral onsite consultations will be useful to sort out all the required information after the data collection, or to discuss the project appraisal and the needed steps for approaching investors. Based on the level of development and independence of each project, the most effective times to schedule the consultation would be either:

- a. After the delivery of the TIP reports and the shortlisting of the 4 projects that will be moved to the full due diligence support, therefore during months 19 and 20, which would allow for a clear review of all the data gaps and the collaboration on the needed pieces of work to lead.
- b. At the end of the due diligence process, between months 21 and 24 with the aim of producing specific technical output needed for investor appraisal, potentially alongside the subcontracted entities where needed.

The 2-day in-person review of the activities could entail the following steps, ideally attended by all members of the project team. The type of services will be tailored to each project's needs, ensuring the possibility of offering as much value as possible to the shortlisted projects through this consultation session.

Day 1 potential topics:

- Technical Development Assistance: Evaluating project designs, identifying opportunities for improvement, and incorporating circular economy principles, discussing the impact.
- Elaborating on the feasibility study: Providing guidance on impact analysis, and circularity assessments to create robust supporting documents for investors.
- Delving in the technology aspect of the project, drafting or reflecting on the technology roadmapping exercise.

Day 2 potential topics:

- Engaging with the stakeholders: Reviewing the local community of practice members, discuss the stakeholder mapping and discuss the engagement strategy.
- Subcontracting and Funding Allocation: Clarifying the process for obtaining targeted funding for local expertise and allocating funds from the earmarked subcontracting budget.
- Final Project Appraisal Preparation: Running through all information and documents for the due diligence report, ensuring alignment with investor requirements, and discussing next steps.

The suggested schedule offers an overview of all the services that could be provided. The project leaders can decide to go through all such elements, or to opt out of some of them in case they might feel they already have access to sufficient information on one of these topics.

Locally provided assistance through subcontracting

DEFINITE-CCRI has specially allocated funds for subcontracting which can be used to provide targeted funding for local expertise on an ad-hoc basis. To ensure the timely agreement between the interested parties and the local subcontractors, given that the budget and the framework of the agreement will also have to be negotiated, the interest for reaching out to local subcontractors should be communicated to the DEFINITE-CCRI team at the latest by month 18 of the DEFINITE-CCRI schedule, for consultations to take place between months 20 and 24. The DEFINITE-CCRI team will then be in charge of reviewing the value added to be produced by subcontractors and of approving the contracts between project managers and the subcontractor to ensure the appropriate use of funding.

While there will be freedom on what subcontractor to reach out to and for what kind of activity, the DEFINITE-CCRI team suggests the potential fields of intervention might be, but not limited to, the following depending on resource availability and in conjunction with the other project partners, NTUA and ICLEI, as part of Work Package 4.3:

- Conducting an LCA, or MFA to further delve into the circularity potential and gauge the impact.
- Conducting a market analysis or a stakeholder engagement plan with a local expert.
- Delving into the technological aspects of the project bringing on board relevant experts.

In case all these elements have been covered and additional budget is left, the remaining budget could be allocated towards additional third-party reviews or advisory where necessary.

While there is no obligation on part of project developers to utilize subcontractors, budget is available, and we therefore will recommend project developers take advantage of the opportunity.

Timeline

The due diligence support package will take place between months 18 and 24 (i.e., April 2024 to September 2024) of the DEFINITE-CCRI project. In the table below the timeline for the 2-day bilateral consultation sessions and the services provided is presented.

Table 7: Timeline of the Due Diligence support package

DEFINITE-CCRI Work Months	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
Check with the projects their needs						
Clarify the Services that will be provided						
Preparation for support						
Provision of the support						
Subcontracted local assistance execution period where needed						
2-day intensive bilateral consultation sessions						
Document finalization for project appraisal phase						

Conclusions

This document serves as a comprehensive guide for the Technical and Impact Potential (TIP) assessment and the Technical Due Diligence within the DEFINITE-CCRI Project Finance initiative. By outlining the objectives, methodology, and scope of Tasks 4.2 and 4.3, the document provides a solid foundation for the development of technical and impact related elements crucial for the success of circular economy projects. The rigorously structured project selection methodology within WP2, encompassing key criteria such as business model rationale, revenue generation capabilities, and existing funding, has enabled the shortlisting of seven promising projects for further evaluation.

The establishment of the TIP assessment steps offers a systematic approach to collect and assess essential project-related data, ensuring an efficient and thorough evaluation process of its impact potential. The step-by-step process allows for close collaboration between the consortium and project owners, fostering a fruitful exchange of insights and expertise. Furthermore, the technical due diligence support services offered to the shortlisted projects demonstrate the commitment of the DEFINITE-CCRI initiative to provide hands-on assistance, nurturing the projects' potential and attractiveness to potential investors.

This document serves as a key resource in advancing the goals of the DEFINITE-CCRI Project and enhancing the impact and potential of circular economy projects towards a successful and sustainable future. Through collaborative efforts, the consortium and project owners stand poised to unlock the full potential of the 9 shortlisted circular economy initiatives, allow them to structure themselves and to attract potential investors.

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Annex I

Total Material Inputs

Description:

These are the material inputs as commonly classified in material flow accounting. For simplicity, only the most high level categories are requested. In order to capture/estimate this information, first the main products utilised by the business/project will need to be identified, then the material composition of these products calculated through LCA or estimated through desktop research. These estimates can be scaled up to the organisation level over the course of 1 year to determine the total material inputs. These figures should include any waste collected that is used as an input into the business operations.

Notes:

Material groups Types of materials. For a highly detailed guide on what the classifications include, see Appendix A in the EW-MFA guide: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/1798247/6191533/20>

Unit Tonnes and Euros are requested separately

Value The required input in the unit specified in the table

Table M.1: Material inputs in tonnes

Material groups	M1.1	M1.2	M1.3	M1.4	M1.5	M1.6	M1.7
	Volume of Inputs	Share of inputs that are virgin materials (volume)	Share of inputs that are secondary materials (volume)	Total volume (materials/waste) collected for processing (that would have otherwise gone for landfill)	Share of materials that are imported (volume)	Share of materials sourced nationally (volume)	Share of materials sourced on site (volume)
	Tonnes	%	%	%	%	%	%
Biomass							
Metals							
Non-metallic minerals							
Fossil fuels							
Total							

Table M.2: Material inputs in euros

Material groups	M2.1	M2.2	M2.3	M2.4	M2.5	M2.6	M2.7
	Value of inputs	Share of inputs that are virgin materials (value)	Share of inputs that are secondary materials (value)	Total value (materials/waste) collected for processing (that would have otherwise gone for landfill)	Share of materials that are imported (value)	Share of materials sourced nationally (value)	Share of materials sourced on site (value)
	Euros	%	%	%	%	%	%
Biomass							
Metals							
Non-metallic minerals							
Fossil fuels							
Total							

Solid Waste

Description:

This data template asks for information regarding waste generation, separation/collection, and treatment for the organisation. The information is asked for in both volume and euro value of contracts to dispose of or treat. The treatment types available correspond to the waste framework in Eurostat. If any sub indicators are unknown for destinations or treatment types, and no estimates are available, please leave blank. Read more about Eurostat waste framework here: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/waste/data/database>

Notes:

Waste categories	Waste categories as commonly classified in the EU
Unit	Tonnes and Euros are requested separately
Value	The required input in the unit specified in the table

Table SW.1: Waste Generated

Waste Generation Types	SW1.1	SW1.2
	Volume of waste	Share of waste that is exported (volume)
	Tonnes	%
Total waste		
Chemical and medical wastes		
Recyclable wastes		
Animal and vegetal wastes (subtotal)		
<i>Animal and mixed food waste</i>		
<i>Vegetal wastes</i>		
<i>Animal faeces, urine and manure</i>		
Mixed ordinary wastes		
Common sludges		
Mineral and solidified wastes		

Table SW.2: Waste Treatment in Tonnes

Waste Treatment Type Categories	SW1.1	SW1.2
	Volume of waste	Share of waste that is exported (volume)
	Tonnes	%
Waste used for energy recovery (RCV_E)		
Waste incinerated without energy recovery (DSP_I)		
Waste recovered (excluding energy recovery and backfilling) (
Waste going to backfilling (RCV_B)		
Waste deposited onto or into land (DSP_L)		
Land treatment and release into water bodies (DSP_OTH)		
Total		

Waste Composted	SW1.1	SW1.2
	Volume of waste	Share of waste that is exported (volume)
	Tonnes	%
Total Waste Composted		

Table SW.3: Waste Treatment in euros

Waste Treatment Type Categories	SW2.1	SW2.2
	Cost of waste collection/treatment	Share of waste that is exported
	Euros	%
Waste used for energy recovery (RCV_E)		
Waste incinerated without energy recovery (DSP_I)		
Waste recovered (excluding energy recovery and backfilling) (
Waste going to backfilling (RCV_B)		
Waste deposited onto or into land (DSP_L)		
Land treatment and release into water bodies (DSP_OTH)		
Total		

Water

Description:

This template requests the water used for operations of the business and is measured over the course of one calendar year

Notes:

Indicator	Required indicator as specified in the table
Unit	KLitres and Euros are requested separately
Value	The required input in the unit specified in the table

Table W.1: Water consumption in KLitres

Indicator	Volume of water consumption
	KLitres
Total Water Consumption	

Table W.2: Water consumption in euros

Indicator	Cost of water consumption
	Euros
Total Water Consumption	

Table W.3: Waste water in KLitres

Indicator	Volume of waste water generated	Share of waste water treated on site (for reuse on site)
	KLitres	%
Waste Water		

Energy

Description:

This template measures the total energy usage of the organisation/project, including a breakdown of the types of energy inputs (renewable vs non renewable). This template refers to total electricity consumption for all business operations over the course of one year.

Notes:

Indicator	Required indicator as specified in the table
Unit	KwH and Euros are requested separately
Value	The required input in the unit specified in the table

Table E.1: Energy use in MWh

Indicator	Energy use
	KwH
Total Energy Used	

Table E.2: Energy use in Euros

Indicator	Cost of energy use
	Euros
Total Energy Cost	

Table E.3: Renewable energy

Indicator	Energy
	KwH
Total energy generated and used on site (through	
Total energy generated and used on site (except t	
Total other renewable energy used	

Table E.4: Biomass related inputs

Indicator	Volume of biomass input
	Tonnes
Total local biomass used for energy production	

Operations

Description:

This template requests data related to the operations, finance or other aspects of the organisation.

Notes:

Indicator	Required indicator as specified in the table
Unit	The unit must be added if not yet specified
Value	The required input in the unit specified in the table

Table C.1: Finance and Economics

Indicator	Unit	Value
Total Revenue	Euros	
Total Production Output	#	
Total Employed on Project	# FTE	
Total Gross Profits	Euros	
Total Net Profits after Taxes	Euros	

Table C.2: Market Share Estimates

Indicator	Unit	Value
Estimated size of global market	Euros	
Estimated size of national market	Euros	
Estimates share of the market (when mature)	%	

Table C.3: Operations

Indicator	Unit	Value
Total kilometres travelled by business vehicles	KMs	
Total kilometres travelled on renewable fuel	KMs	
Total floor area of all operations	Square meters	

Table C.4: Repair

Indicator	Unit	Value
Numer of items received	#	
Total number of products repaired	#	
Estimated total product life extension (sum)	Years	

Emissions

Description:

This template relates to capturing the final results from GHG Accounting or GHG Inventories of the project. Read more about GHG Inventories and the different "scopes" here: <https://ghgprotocol.org/>

Notes:

Indicator	Required indicator as specified in the table
Unit	The unit must be added if not yet specified
Value	The required input in the unit specified in the table

Table Em.1 Emissions

Indicator	Unit	Value
Scope 1 Emissions	CO2 eq.	
Scope 2 Emissions	CO2 eq.	
Scope 3 Emissions	CO2 eq.	

Technology

Description:

This template is a qualitative assessment of various aspects of the technology from innovation to readiness

Notes:

Indicator	Required indicator as specified in the table
Description	The description of the indicator
Scale	The qualitative rating scale
Value	The rating

Table T1.

Indicator	Description	Scale	Value
Implementation of smart technologies for resource management	The level of incorporation of Industry 4.0 technologies or of IoT technologies in the resource management activities. The level of deploying data analytics and relevant tools in the resource management practices, The level of utilization of smart technologies in in the resource management practices. 1 being no industry 4.0 or IoT technologies and data analytics tool are used whatsoever, 3 being them used in some aspects of the resource management or the approach, and 5 being using IoT technologies and data analytics where applicable.	Scale from 1 to 5	
Adoption of circular economy technologies and innovations	The level of integration of circular economy technologies and innovative practices that support the principles of circular economy. 1 being the approach is not that innovative to 5 the approach is highly innovative and uses state of the art technologies.	Scale from 1 to 5	
Integration of IoT and data analytics for production optimization	The level of incorporation of Industry 4.0 technologies or of IoT technologies in the production activities. The level of deploying data analytics and relevant tools in the production practices, The level of utilization of smart technologies in the production practices. 1 being no industry 4.0 or IoT technologies and data analytics tool whatsoever, 3 being in some aspects of the production or the approach, and 5 being using IoT technologies and data analytics where applicable.	Scale from 1 to 5	
TRL of the technology	TRL is a type of measurement system used to assess the maturity level of a particular technology. TRL 1 Basic Principle Observed, TRL 2 Technology concept formulated, TRL3 Experimental proof of concept, TRL 4 Technology validated in lab, TRL 5 Technology validated in relevant environment, TRL 6 Technology demonstrated in relevant environment, TRL 7 System prototype demonstration in operational environment, TRL 8 System complete and qualified, TRL 9 Actual system proven in operational environment	Scale from 1 to 9	
Use of data analytics for evidence-based decision-making	The level of employment of data analytics tools in the approach, 1 being no industry 4.0 or IoT technologies and data analytics tool whatsoever, 3 being in some aspects of the resource management or the approach, and 5 being using IoT technologies and data analytics where applicable.	Scale from 1 to 5	